

TRAVELOGUES BY MUKIMI

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Abstract: In this paper travelogues written by the prominent poet and literary critic Mukimi are researched. Mukimi's literary activity is vast and his contribution to the development of Uzbek literature is of great value. These issues are analyzed in the paper.

Key words: Mukimi, travelogues, literary activity, literature, poet, ghazal, literary work, to criticize, stanza.

Mukimi wrote poems about the impressions of his travels along the Fergana Valley, and these became famous under the name "Travel logs". These are impressions of the poet's journeys Kokand-Fergana, Kokand-Shahimardan, Kokand-Isfara. All three travelogues are in the form of a single work, consisting of four parts. A total amount is of 244 verses. Everything is of the same verse — rajazi murabbai solim, and each clause ends with the radif "if". All have one common introduction and one common conclusion. In the work, the reason for the trip is given, and then various destinations, villages, their nature and scenery are described. The people and actions of the places are told.

"Sayohatnama" (travelogue):

Faryodkim, garduni dun,

Aylar yurak-bag'rimni xun.

Ko'rdiki bir ahli funun

Charx anga kajraftor ekan, —

There is a special genre called "hasbi hol" in our classical literature. In it, the poet writes about his situation. Sometimes some of its manifestations can be found in other poems. There is such a situation in "Sayohatnama". The poet cries out from "garduni dun" ("merciless world"), complains that it has made his heart be ill "blood" ("khun"). He points out that this world is always going backwards ("kajraftar") to "Ahli funun" ("people of science"). The poet continues this idea in the sixth stanza, stating the reason for the trip as follows:

Qolmay shaharda toqatim,

Qishloq chiqardim odatim.

Xohi yayov, bo'lsun otim,

Goh sayr ham darkor ekan.

The author's mood, situation, attitude to the environment and people are clearly felt in the lines of "Sayohatnoma". For example, on his way to

Shahimardan, the poet introduces the villages of Ultarma, Dormoncha, Borbaliq, Aqyer, Roshidon, Zohidan, Altiariq, Chimyon, Vodil, and describes each of them:

Ammo nazarda Roshidon
Firdavs bog'idin nishon.
O'ynab oqar obi ravon,
Sahni gulu gulzor ekan.
Vodil maqomi dilfizo,
Ko'chalaridur dilqusho,
Anhorida obi safo,
Sebarga obishor ekan.

Furthermore, in the next travelogue, details are given about villages and towns such as Kudash, Yaipan, Nursukh, Beshariq, Konibodom. The poet joyfully praises Rapkan, buried in the cool shade, and Yaypan, whose willow groves fascinate everyone. He describes the beautiful nature of the Motherland, its dazzling landscapes, "deserts of Anhoru Soy" and "sweet sardines" with infinite love and pride.

Nursux kabi bir joy kam,
Tushmay o'tib qildi alam,
Olma anor o'rniga ham,
Bog'ida toku zang ekan.

Mukimi's "Sayohatnoma" resonated among Kokand poets. Great poets such as Furqat, Zavqi, Tajalli wrote poems with the verse and radif of Muqimi's work. Furqat "Sayohatnoma" Furqatologist Sh. Posted by Yusupov. The "Sayohatnoma" of Zavqi is known as "Comic about Obid Mingboshi". Only fragments of Tajalli's "Sayohatnoma" have arrived.

On the other hand, if we remember that "Sayohatnoma" were written in the Persian-Tajik language in the literary environment of Bukhara in the 19th century, it becomes clear that this genre gained wide popularity during this period. It is impossible that Mukimi, who returned from studying in Bukhara in the 70s, was not aware of them.

In short, Muqimi's poetry became important in the formation of the new Uzbek literature, especially in the central place of social satire and diversity. A number of literary works have been written about the poet, including Sabir Abdulla's novel "Mavlano Muqimi".

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